

Legal Licenses, Intellectual Property, Laws ,and Adminstrations

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Abstract:

Legal Licences are necessary, for preserving any intellectual property, as per owners. Either it be, firm based, institution based, or Government based, certain rules and laws are outlined to be followed. In this paper, we have discussed for more efficient Licences, that can work, as per any nation's laws, or even as per international sectors.

Keywords: Licences, Legal Licences, Intellectual Property, Arjun Dahal, arjundahalard

Introduction:

On discussing brief, organizations like WIPO, Creative Commons, as well as agreements like PCT and such are found across the world, with nations being member of each of such organizations, or endorsing the agreement for protection of intellectual property.

Author intended to made postal services more scientific, and wrote few application letters, to Postal Service, along with administrations like as Office of Copyright Registrar Registration, and Department of Industry, in Nepal.

Thus we shall begin in brief generalization, how can we make more effective licences for preservation of Intellectual Property. Our topics begins from registration, of any firm, organization, institution, in their respective nations, as per their authorities; like as Office of Copyright Registrar Registration, Department of Industry, which works for Patents, and Trademarks, as well as Communication Authorities, which provides services for emails, Internet, or even postal means.

Thus, let us begin with an example of author's own firm, Mental Asylum of Education.

When I would register my blog(of these days, i.e. arjundahal.blogspot.com), or any website with its URL, in office of copyright registrar registration, would allow us copyright protection, including topics updated in any website, either be in website's archive or any means, even for physical administrative works, by informing updates to respective authority (Office of copyright registrar registration)

That would then provide value to meaning of ©, which is discussed for copyrights, and is talked as Copyright Protected.

Patents are generally talked for invention, and author do guess, each is work is invention and a creation of creators, or any fellow, who has worked to make it create it; and that can be anything, either be book, manuscript, art, engineering and architecture, or any topics, based on newthing.

Significant difference, observed would be in entirely new thing, and modification and updates, for which, among patents too, works can be categorised as per their nature.

Registration Number, Token Number, Reference Numbers, would be necessary for each of materials, including emails, contact forms in website, or communication, which then would form a database too, and would require sources for management, for smoother and safer work flow.

In Nepal, I cannot register in Department of Patents, for my organization, and do guess, same in other nations, whereas, allowing registration of organizations, would provide immediate secureness, based on classification of patents, so that, if any new materials has been provided, then they are patented, as per generalised patentees for all materials, then individualized patents for works as per meaning of patents(these days)

Then comes topics of communication, which too based on registration would be patented and copyrights, making complete archival of any data. In that process metadata would be needed, only when works are categorised, otherwise, each and every information would be safely archived, and need of privacy policy would be felt to preserve the privacy of information, and to protect information from being misused, then all informations would be safe, as per Laws; which has to address Copyrights related, Patent related, and Communication related matters.

Conclusion:

Verbal Communication would be hard to be provide copyrighted, or patent unless we do record and keep our recording devices on, while talking, and that is like as troll, and and like as of verbal communication, Are our data and database safe, along with privacy, would be important question and governing administrations too has to take care of database, because copyrighted, patents are needed, to be shared across the world, so that, as per Laws of other nations, Intellectuality Property can be preserved.

Beautiful Trouble:

Beautiful Trouble would be felt, when question for archival takes places, where each administrations would need to keep information archived, and question would arise, If to open or not Archival Centre, based on our discussion for complete archival of data being copyrighted and patented. Trademark too being an art would be needed as per discussion of Copyrights, and even Patent.

Actknowledgement:

My Actknowledgements goes to various Licence Providers or Licence Makers, like as MIT Licence, GNU Licence, Creative Commons Licences, Apache Licences and other Licence Providers, as well as do acknowledge my own application letters submitted to various administrations.